

A Descriptive Study on Demographical, Haematological and Biochemical Profile of Weedicide Poisoning At Tertiary Health Care Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Across the world, poisoning from pesticides and other chemicals used in agriculture is a serious public health hazard, especially in poor countries. Weedicides such as paraquat, 2,4-D, and glyphosate have been shown to be among the several compounds that significantly contribute to higher rates of sickness and mortality. Publications about weedicide toxicity are few.

Aims and Objective: To investigate the biochemical, haematological, and demographic characteristics of weedicide poisoning.

Materials and Methods: The current study, which is a retrospective observational study, involves individuals who suffered weedicide poisoning and were admitted at a tertiary health care facility. From the patient's medical records, the researchers collected information on biochemical markers, clinical presentations, haematological parameters, and demographics.

Result: There were a total of 28 cases of weedicide poisoning, of which 19 (67.86%) included paraquat, 7 (25%), and 2 (7.14%) used 2,4-D. In terms of results, 10 (35.74%) of them were discharged, 6 (21.43%) of them died, 12 (42.86%) got referred to a higher centre for hemoperfusion/hemodialysis, and 1 (3.57%) absconded.

Conclusion: There is evidence linking weedicide consumption to high rates of sickness and fatalities. The prompt underscores the need of expeditiously detecting and executing preemptive actions to tackle instances of weedicide toxicity, considering the lack of a specific remedy.

Keywords: Glyphosate; Paraquat; Poisoning; Weedicide.

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Introduction

Especially in developing countries, the problem of pesticide and other chemical-related poisoning in agriculture poses a serious threat to public health worldwide. It is projected that the yearly death rate from hazardous exposure will be more than 50,000. Drawing from data from the National Poisons Information Centre in New Delhi, an analysis of recorded poisoning cases showed that household agents were responsible for the majority of poisoning cases (44.1%), which were then followed by pharmaceutical drugs (18.8%), agricultural pesticides (weedicide in particular) (12.8%), industrial chemicals (8.9%), animal bites and stings (4.7%), plants (1.7%), cases of unknown origin (2.9%), and other categories (5.6%). [4] A broad range of household products that are commonly used for household purposes include pesticides, household cleaners, mercury thermometers, antiseptic medicines, kerosene, paint thinners and so on. These compounds have the potential to cause

poisoning if misused or handled improperly. The National Poisons Centre (NPIC) is housed at the All India Institute of Medical Sciences in New Delhi. It provides treatment physicians throughout India with guidelines on how to handle poisoning situations. An estimated 20,000 or more people die worldwide each year from pesticide and chemical poisoning in agriculture, and over 2 million hospital admissions are due to the same cause. While only making up 0.34% of all cases that were reported, paraquat poisoning had the highest mortality rate—it was responsible for 13% of all recorded fatalities. [3] Chemicals called weedicides are used to suppress unwanted plants. 2-4-D amine salt (58%), glyphosate (glycine) (41%), paraquat (safaya) (24%), metribuzin 70% WP, phenoxaprop-p-ethyl 9.3%, propaquizafop 10% EC, tembotrione 34.4%, sodium acifluorfen 16.5% + clodinafop-propargyl 8% EC, and topramezone are common weedicides utilised. 2, 4-D is a herbicide that falls

within the Chlorophenoxy category according to its chemical makeup. Numerous physiological systems are affected, such as the heart, liver, kidneys, muscles, lungs, endocrine system, central and peripheral nervous systems, and liver.

A variety of physiological manifestations, including nausea, vomiting, stomach pain, hepatic injury, kidney damage, hypertonia, areflexia, central nervous system suppression, fasciculations, coma, hypotension, and abnormal ECG readings, are indicative of intoxication. [6] A substantial quantity of 2,4-D ingested has the potential to cause fatal acute poisoning. [7] These drugs have been linked to a number of detrimental activities, including uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation, disruption of acetyl coenzyme A metabolism, and dosage-dependent damage to cell membranes.

As of right moment, there isn't a specific antidote known to be available for 2,4-D toxicity. [8] For cases of severe poisoning, it is desirable to consider using haemodialysis or alkaline diuresis to aid in the elimination of pesticides. [8] In many regions of Asia and the Pacific, consuming paraquat (1, 1-dimethyl-4, 4-bipyridium dichloride) is a leading cause of lethal poisoning. [9] It is a broad-spectrum, non-selective herbicide that kills undesirable green plants instantly upon contact by causing superoxide anion production during photosynthesis. [10] Paraquat prevents the conversion of NADP to NADPH by interfering with the intracellular electron transport mechanisms. Lipid cell membranes will thereafter be destroyed as a result of the build-up of superoxide radicals. [11] Organ damage results from the generation of highly reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, with the lungs being especially vulnerable because of their absorption against a concentration gradient. [12]

There are no known particular counteragents, and the treatments now in use have not shown to be effective in treating severe fulminant PQ poisoning. [13] The commercial formulations of glyphosate, a non-selective herbicide, incorporate surfactants that varied in kind and concentration. Glyphosate is available in five distinct salt forms. Because of this, complex and varied combinations rather than just the active component alone can harm humans when using this herbicide. [14] It is believed that the uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation is the mechanism behind the toxicity of glyphosate in animals. [15] When this material is consumed, the GI system is eroded, which causes difficulty swallowing and gastrointestinal haemorrhage. There is an occasional correlation between dermal exposure and skin and eye discomfort. The process of breathing in spray mist can cause pain in the

nasal and oral cavities, as well as tingling and irritation in the throat. Many physiological symptoms, such as dehydration, hypotension, oliguria, pneumonitis, altered consciousness, liver failure, acidosis, hyperkalaemia, and dysrhythmias, can be brought on by severe poisoning. [16] Glyphosate has no known counter-adote, and supportive care is the norm. The majority of the research focused on pesticide toxicity in the broader community. Since there aren't many published studies on weedicide poisoning, the purpose of this one was to evaluate the prevalence of weedicide poisoning in the general population, with a focus on the demographic, haematological, and biochemical profiles of the cases as well as their outcomes.

Aims and Objective: To investigate the biochemical, haematological, and demographic characteristics of weedicide poisoning.

Materials and Methods:

Prior to initiating the study, clearance from the Institutional Research and Ethical Committee was secured. This study used a retrospective observational design, conducted at a tertiary health facility with patients diagnosed with weedicide poisoning who were admitted to the department of medicine. The included patients' clinical, haematological, biochemical and demographic data were gathered from the case files that were acquired from the medical record department. The third day of hospitalisation saw the analysis of the biochemical and haematological examinations. The proforma was filled up with the recorded data.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients who were hospitalised and had previously consumed weedicide.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals have a medical background that includes both chronic liver and kidney illness, as well as drugs that have impacted liver function and renal function testing.

Statistical Analysis: The acquired data were examined with SPSS software after being input into a Microsoft Excel sheet. Frequency analysis and percentage analysis were used to examine the relationship.

Results

Twenty-eight people with a diagnosis of weedicide toxicity were chosen as study participants over the course of the allotted research period. Of the weedicides consumed, 19 were paraquat, 7 were 2-4D cases, and 2 were glyphosate. The frequency distribution of different weedicide ingestions is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of weedicide compounds ingested

Type of weedicide	Paraquat (safaya)	2,4-D	Glyphosate (glycine)	Total
Number of cases (%)	19 (67.86%)	7 (25%)	2 (7.14%)	28 (100%)

Since all patients purposefully consumed the poison orally, this is the most common type of poisoning (100%). The gender distribution of the research population showed that, at 85.71% of the total, men made up the majority of participants.

The male-to-female ratio in the sample was around 6:1, with 24 male patients and 4 female patients. The average age of the study participants was

found to be 31±11 years, by the researchers. According to the study, 35 and under accounted for half of the cases (35.71%), with the remaining half (35.7%) occurring in the 26–35 age range.

Afterwards, 21.43% of cases were in the age range of 36 to 45 years, and 3.57% of all patients were in the 46-55 and 56-65 year age groups. (Refer to Table 2)

Table 2: Gender distribution among various age groups of all the weedicide poisoning patients

S.No.	Age Group (in yrs.)	Male (n=24)	Female (n=4)	Total (n=28)
1.	15-25	9	1	10
2.	26-35	9	1	10
3.	36-45	5	1	6
4.	46-55	1	0	1
5.	56-65	0	1	1

Thirteen farmers (46.43%) made up the largest portion of the research participant group, followed by four students (14.28%), four housewives (14.28%), three coolies (10.71%), three jobless people (10.71%), and one private employee (3.57%). Patients with weedicide poisoning complained of dysphagia 23 (82.14%), hematemesis 1 (3.57%), melena 1 (3.57%), dyspnea 1 (3.57%), vomiting 28 (100%), ulcers of the mouth 27 (96.43%), discomfort in the throat 26 (92.86%), and stomach pain 19 (67.86%). (Table 3)

Table 3: Distribution of study population according to weedicide poison ingested and symptoms

Symptoms	Paraquat (n=19)	2-4-D (n=7)	Glyphosate (n=2)	Total
Vomiting	19	7	2	28 (100%)
Oral ulcer	19	7	1	27 (96.43%)
Throat discomfort	19	6	1	26 (92.86%)
Abdominal pain	17	2	0	19 (67.86)
Dysphagia	19	3	1	23 (82.14%)
Hematemesis	1	0	0	1 (3.57%)
Malena	1	0	0	1 (3.57%)
Dyspnoea	1	0	0	1 (3.57%)

Multi-organ failure affected 17% of the patients in the study group. In paraquat instances, TLC was much higher—the mean was 22186.37±4646.40. Mean TLC values for 2,4-D and glyphosate were 9466.71±1720.41 and 11057±1099.55, respectively.

Serum bilirubin was elevated 3.33±1.01 in paraquat patients, SGOT was up 198.02±58.54, SGPT was elevated 115.60±25.75, blood urea was elevated 129.14±43.93, and serum creatinine was elevated

6.57±2.31. The mean blood urea was 28.09±2.61, serum creatinine was elevated to 1.22±0.17, mean SGOT was 35.21±18.56, mean SGPT was 30.76±13.72, and mean serum bilirubin was 0.98±0.40 in 2,4-D patients.

The mean serum bilirubin in glyphosate instances was 1.22±0.22, the mean serum SGOT was 49.5±6.36, the mean SGPT was 40.2±3.11, the mean blood urea was elevated at 38±8.49, and the mean serum creatinine was 1.45±0.70. (Table 4)

Table 4: Distribution of study population according to ingested poison and laboratory investigations (N = 28)

Parameters	Paraquat (N=19)	2-4-D (N=7)	Glyphosate (N=2)
Haemoglobin (gm/dl)	12.36±1.66	12.83±0.433	12.16±3.03
TLC	22186.37±4646.40	16466.71±1583.92	11057.5±1099.56
Platelet	2.17±0.51	2.17±0.34	2.20±0.23
T. Bilirubin (mg/dl)	3.33±1.01	0.98±0.40	1.22±0.22
SGOT (U/L)	198.02±58.54	35.21±18.56	49.5±6.36
SGPT (U/L)	115.60±25.75	30.76±13.72	40.2±3.11
Blood Urea (mg/dl)	129.14±43.93	28.09±2.61	38±8.49
S. Creatinine (mg/dl)	6.57±2.31	1.22±0.17	1.45±0.70
ECG (AF)	1	0	0

Out of the research period's admitted cases of weedicide poisoning, 10 (35.74%) were discharged, 6 (21.43%) expired, 12 (42.86%) were sent to a higher facility for hemodialysate/hemoperfusion, and 1 (3.57%) absconded. (Table 5)

Table 5: Outcome in different weedicide poisonings

Outcome	Paraquat (n=19)	2,4-D (n=7)	Glyphosate (n=2)	Total
Discharge	1	6	2	9
Expired	6	0	0	6
Referred to higher centre	11	1	0	12
Absconded	1	0	0	1

Discussion:

In situations of weedicide poisoning, paraquat, 2,4-D, and glyphosate are the most often encountered toxins. Due to their high level of toxicity, the aforementioned compounds require the employment of suitable treatment methods in situations of poisoning. The condition's inherent toxicity and the lack of effective treatment alternatives are the main causes of these individuals' high mortality rate. Common symptoms of these poisonings include acid-base imbalance, tachycardia, shock, pulmonary edema, and gastrointestinal corrosive effects, including the mouth and throat, dysphagia, and epigastric pain. The long-term health effects include death, multi-organ failure, or lung fibrosis. As of right now, these poisonings cannot be treated with a recognised antidote. Providing support is the mainstay of the therapy strategy. Initially, it is recommended to use whole-gut irrigation or stomach lavage with adsorption agents such as bentonite, activated charcoal, or Fuller's earth. Medical therapies such as hemodialysate or hemoperfusion may be considered useful in cases of renal failure. Herbicides have been used extensively in suicide attempts in India [17]. Three of the five patients in Punjab who had their cases reported in a study done in hospitals between 1999 and 2006 passed away [18]. Ten patients had a 100% death rate, according to another study done in Tamil Nadu [19]. A recent media report states that over 100 recorded deaths from paraquat poisoning occurred in the Orissa region between 2018 and 2019 [20]. This makes the problem a major worry.

There were a total of 28 cases of weedicide toxicity reported throughout the allocated study period. Out of these instances, two (7.14%) were connected to glyphosate, seven (25%) to 2,4-D, and nineteen (67.86%) to paraquat. The gender distribution of the sample population showed that men (85.71%, n=24) predominated over women (14.29%, n=4). The sample's gender distribution was typified by a 6:1 male-to-female ratio. The participants' ages ranged from 31 years on average to 11 years on standard. According to the study by Harika Cherukuri et al., men made up 60% of the research participants and accounted for a sizable share of the

cases. In particular, the male-to-female ratio was around 3:2, with 36 male patients and 24 female patients. [17] The median age of the study population was 25.38 ± 9.136 years. [17] Kim et al. (2009) discovered that the male to female ratio at Soonchunhyang Hospital (SCH) in Cheonan, Korea, was 1.3:1. Men were 26.58 ± 9.473 years old on average, and women were 23.58 ± 8.480 years old on average. [21]

Our study found that vomiting (100%), oral ulcers (96.43%), throat discomfort (92.86%), stomach pain (67.86%), dysphagia (82.14%), haematemesis (3.57%), melena (3.57%), and dyspnea (3.57%) are the most prevalent clinical signs of weedicide poisoning. These results are in line with those of Harika et al., who reported that of 60 patients who had herbicide poisoning, 68.3% had vomiting, 31.7% had oral ulcers, 26.7% had throat discomfort, 23.3% had abdominal pain, 16.7% had dysphagia, and 10.0% had dyspnea. Four people in the cohort under examination—or 6.7% of the study population overall—were determined to have a mental illness. [17] According to Sandhu et al.'s (year) research, vomiting was the most common symptom of paraquat poisoning, occurring in 100% of patients. Oral ulcers (59%), dysphagia (53%), and dyspnea (41%) were the next most common symptoms. The results are similar. [22]

We found that the mean haemoglobin levels in paraquat, 2,4-D, and glyphosate poisoning were 12.36 ± 1.66 , 12.83 ± 0.433 , and 12.16 ± 3.03 , respectively. In paraquat instances, TLC was much higher—the mean was 22186.37 ± 4646.40 . Mean TLC values for 2,4-D and glyphosate were 9466.71 ± 1720.41 and 11057 ± 1099.55 , respectively. Serum bilirubin mean 3.33 ± 1.01 , SGOT mean 198.02 ± 58.54 , and SGPT mean 115.60 ± 25.75 were all elevated in paraquat patients. Serum creatinine was elevated at 6.57 ± 2.31 and blood urea was elevated at mean 129.14 ± 43.93 . The mean blood urea was 28.09 ± 2.61 , serum creatinine was elevated to 1.22 ± 0.17 , mean SGOT was 35.21 ± 18.56 , mean SGPT was 30.76 ± 13.72 , and mean serum bilirubin was 0.98 ± 0.40 in 2,4-D patients. The mean serum bilirubin in glyphosate instances was 1.22 ± 0.22 , the mean serum SGOT was 49.5 ± 6.36 , the mean SGPT was 40.2 ± 3.11 , the mean blood urea was

elevated at 38 ± 8.49 , and the mean serum creatinine was 1.45 ± 0.70 .

The gastrointestinal tract can be severely damaged by paraquat, and it can also cause acute kidney injury, renal tubular necrosis, liver dysfunction, respiratory failure, and pulmonary fibrosis, among other toxic symptoms. The poisoning of paraquat is frequently linked to a high death rate. It has been demonstrated that the mortality rates in India and a number of other global locations vary from 35% to 100% [24]. It has been demonstrated that the death event may occur as soon as six weeks after consumption. [23].

According to our research, 94.87% of patients with paraquat poisoning had abnormal liver function test results and all of them showed signs of leucocytosis. Furthermore, on electrocardiography (ECG), 3.57% of patients had atrial fibrillation, and 94.87% of patients had laboratory results suggestive of severe renal injury. Results-wise, there were nine cases (35.74%) that led to discharge, six cases (21.43%) that resulted in expiration, twelve cases (42.86%) that were sent to a higher facility for hemodialysate/hemoperfusion, and one patient (3.57%) that absperited. According to a research by Sarkar TS et al., abnormal liver enzyme levels were found in 64% of the patients' liver function tests. Furthermore, laboratory results indicating of acute renal injury were seen in 58% of the patients, and chest X-ray features indicative of alveolar damage were seen in 30% of the patients. In addition, 62% of the patients were released from the hospital after making a full recovery, whereas 38% of the patients tragically passed away. [25]

In addition to Fuller's earth, it is advised to offer activated charcoal to reduce further absorption. Because gastric lavage has the potential to produce caustic injury, it should not be performed [26]. Elimination techniques such as hemodialysate and hemoperfusion are unlikely to change the course of the clinical course [26]. The process of immunosuppression with dexamethasone, cyclophosphamide, and methylprednisolone is often utilised; nonetheless, there is a dearth of evidence to support its efficacy [26]. Because they may scavenge free radicals, have anti-inflammatory qualities, and decrease NF- κ B activity, antioxidants such as acetylcysteine and salicylate may be beneficial. [26]

Limitation of study: Because this study is restricted to a single city and one educational institution, extrapolating the findings to a wider geographic area might not be feasible.

Conclusion

Poisoning from weedicides linked to increase morbidity and death. The most typical signs and symptoms are dysphagia, vomiting, mouth ulcers,

sore throats, and stomach pain. Leucocytosis, disordered LFT, and deranged RFT are the three most significant laboratory results, especially in paraquat poisoning cases. Particularly Paraquat, weedicides cause multiorgan failure and death. Distinguishing between pesticide and weedicide poisoning in the emergency room is crucial. Since there is no known cure for paraquat poisoning, prompt diagnosis and intensive treatment are essential.

Recommendation:

In order to effectively monitor trends and adopt legislation and take action to avoid and treat such events, it is vital to curb the present scenario that we may be facing. This may be done by conducting further research across various regions.

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